

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Constitutive deletion of astrocytic connexins aggravates kainate-induced epilepsy

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Abstract

The astroglial gap junctional network formed by connexin (Cx) channels plays a central role in regulating neuronal activity and network synchronization. However, its involvement in the development and progression of epilepsy is not yet understood. Loss of interastrocytic gap junction (GJ) coupling has been observed in the sclerotic hippocampus of patients with mesial temporal lobe epilepsy (MTLE) and in mouse models of MTLE, leading to the suggestion that it plays a causative role in the pathogenesis. To further elucidate this clinically relevant question, we investigated consequences of astrocyte disconnection on the time course and severity of kainate-induced MTLE with hippocampal sclerosis (HS) by comparing mice deficient for astrocytic Cx proteins with wild-type mice (WT). Continuous telemetric EEG recordings and video monitoring performed over a period of 4 weeks after epilepsy induction revealed substantially higher seizure and interictal spike activity during the chronic phase in Cx deficient versus WT mice, while the severity of *status epilepticus* was not different. Immunohistochemical analysis showed that, despite the elevated chronic seizure activity, astrocyte disconnection did not aggravate the severity of HS. Indeed, the extent of CA1 pyramidal cell loss was similar between the experimental groups, while astrogliosis, granule cell dispersion, angiogenesis, and microglia activation were even reduced in Cx deficient as compared to WT mice. Interestingly, seizure-induced neurogenesis in the adult dentate gyrus was also independent of astrocytic Cxs. Together, our data indicate that constitutive loss of GJ coupling between astrocytes promotes neuronal hyperexcitability and attenuates seizure-induced histopathological outcomes.

KEYWORDS

astrocyte, gap junction channels, hippocampal sclerosis, neurogenesis, *status epilepticus*, temporal lobe epilepsy

1 | INTRODUCTION

The general ability of astrocytes to modulate neuronal function is well established while its specific involvement in the pathogenesis of neurological disorders is a matter of intense research. A striking feature of

astrocytes is their abundant intercellular connection via gap junction (GJ) channels, leading to the formation of large syncytium-like functional networks. Due to this network organization, astrocytes are in a position to effectively control and synchronize large neuronal assemblies, and it appears evident that impaired coupling has deleterious consequences on

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brain functioning (Giaume, Koulakoff, Roux, Holcman, & Rouach, 2010). GJ channels are composed of a family of proteins called connexins (Cx). Six Cxs oligomerize into a hemichannel (connexon) and two connexons from adjacent cell membranes dock to form an intercellular GJ channel. In the hippocampus, the communication between astrocytes is mainly accomplished by Cx43 channels and only to a small extent by channels composed of Cx30 (Gosejacob et al., 2011). GJ channels are permeable to ions and small molecules up to 1 kDa, including second messengers, nucleotides, neurotransmitters, and energy metabolites (Giaume et al., 2010).

The role of astroglial networks in the pathophysiology of epilepsy is still debated (Boison & Steinhäuser, 2018; Steinhäuser, Seifert, & Bedner, 2012). On the one hand, astrocyte coupling limits neuronal excitability by clearance and redistribution of extracellular ions and neurotransmitters (Pannasch et al., 2011; Wallraff et al., 2006), while on the other hand astrocyte-astrocyte connections are required to maintain synaptic transmission by activity-dependent supply of energy metabolites from blood vessels to the firing neurons (Rouach, Koulakoff, Abudara, Willecke, & Giaume, 2008). Hence, in principle, the astroglial network exerts both proepileptic and antiepileptic effects. We have previously shown that the sclerotic hippocampus of patients with medically refractory mesial temporal lobe epilepsy (MTLE) is completely devoid of classical astrocytes and GJ coupling. The functional properties of human and murine astrocytes are strikingly similar (Bedner, Jabs, & Steinhäuser, 2019). In a mouse model of MTLE, we could demonstrate that astrocyte uncoupling and the consequential impairment of K^+ clearance temporally precede neuronal death and the onset of spontaneous seizure activity, pointing to a causative role of uncoupling in the genesis of MTLE (Bedner et al., 2015). In favor of a causative role is also the finding that transgenic mice with coupling-deficient astrocytes (Cx30^{-/-}; Cx43^{fl/fl}hGFAP-Cre mice; termed DKO mice) display disturbed K^+ and glutamate clearance as well as spontaneous epileptiform field potentials and a decreased threshold for evoking epileptiform activity in acute hippocampal slices (Pannasch et al., 2011; Wallraff et al., 2006). A recent study reported that DKO mice are less prone to pentylenetetrazole (PTZ)-induced hyperexcitability, leading to the speculation that specific blockade of astrocytic GJs could be of therapeutic benefit also in chronic seizures (Chever, Dossi, Pannasch, Derangeon, & Rouach, 2016). Hence, the data obtained from DKO mice so far are conflicting and do not allow firm conclusions on the role of the astroglial network in epilepsy. To shed more light on this issue, in the present study we examined the effects of Cx30 and Cx43 deletion in astrocytes on acute and chronic electrographic seizure activity as well as on the consequential morphological changes in a mouse model of MTLE with hippocampal sclerosis (HS).

2 | METHODS

2.1 | Animals

Maintenance and handling of animals was according to the local government regulations. Experiments were approved by the North

Rhine-Westphalia State Agency for Nature, Environment and Consumer Protection (approval numbers 84-02.04.2012.A212 and 84-02.04.2015.A393). All measures were taken to minimize the number of animals used. Mice were kept under standard housing conditions (12 hr/12 hr dark-light cycle, food, and water ad libitum). Male C57Bl6/J mice (Charles River, Sulzfeld, Germany) and transgenic mice lacking Cx30 and Cx43 in GFAP-positive cells (Cx30^{-/-}; Cx43^{fl/fl}hGFAP-Cre mice, Wallraff et al., 2006) aged 90–120 days were used for the experiments.

2.2 | Kainate injection and EEG recordings

We used the MTLE animal model previously established (Bedner et al., 2015). Briefly, mice were anesthetized with a mixture of medetomidine (Cepetor, CP-Pharma, Burgdorf, Germany, 0.3 mg/kg, i.p.) and ketamine (Ketamidol, WDT, Garbsen, Germany, 40 mg/kg, i.p.) and placed in a stereotaxic frame equipped with a manual microinjection unit (TSE Systems GmbH, Bad Homburg, Germany). A total volume of 70 μ l of a 20 mM solution of kainate (Tocris, Bristol, UK) in 0.9% sterile NaCl were stereotactically injected into the neocortex just above the right dorsal hippocampus. The stereotactic coordinates were 2 mm posterior to bregma, 1.5 mm from midline and 1.7 mm from the skull surface. Electrographic seizures were detected via skull surface electrodes implanted directly after kainate injection. Telemetric transmitters (TA10EA-F20, TA11ETA-F10; Data Sciences International, St. Paul, MN) were placed subcutaneously into the right abdominal region and the two monopolar leads were connected to stainless steel screws (length 2 mm; thread diameter 0.8 mm) positioned bilaterally 1.5 mm from the sagittal suture and 2 mm posterior to bregma. The attached leads were covered with dental cement, skin incisions sutured, and anesthesia stopped with atipamezole (Antisedan, Orion Pharma, Hamburg, Germany, 300 mg/kg, i.p.). To reduce pain, mice were subsequently injected for 3 days with carprofen (Rimadyl, Pfizer, Karlsruhe, Germany). Furthermore, 0.25% Enrofloxacin (Baytril, Bayer, Leverkusen, Germany) was administered via drinking water to reduce the risk of infection. Mice were then returned to clean cages and placed on individual radio receiving plates (RPC-1; Data Sciences International), which capture data signals from the transmitter and send them to a computer running Dataquest A.R.T. 4.00 Gold/Platinum software (Data Sciences International), which converts the digital output of the receiver into a calibrated analog output. A network-based video surveillance system (SeeTec, Philippsburg, Germany) was used to monitor behavioral seizure activity.

NeuroScore 3.2 software (Data Sciences International) was used for EEG analysis. Seizure frequency and duration were determined using the NeuroScore seizure detection module with the following parameters: threshold value = $10 \times SD$ of the baseline–1,000 μ V, spike duration = 0.05–50 ms, spike interval = 0.1–2.5 s, minimum train duration = 10 s, and minimum number of spikes per event = 50. All EEG recordings were

additionally verified by manual screening. Automated and manual EEG screening was always performed by two independent investigators, one of which was blinded to the experimental conditions. For spectral analysis, EEG data were subjected to fast Fourier transform (FFT) and the absolute power (i.e., the integral of the power values over the different frequency ranges expressed in μV^2) of the frequency bands δ (0.5–4 Hz), θ (4–8 Hz), α (8–13 Hz), β (13–30 Hz), and γ (30–50 Hz) were calculated in 10 s epochs for the entire 4 weeks of continuous EEG recording. The γ -band power during the first 6 hr of EEG recording was used for *status epilepticus* (SE) quantification, as the power in this frequency range is the most reliable and least artifact-prone indicator for SE severity (Lehmkuhle et al., 2009). In contrast, the interictal activity during the chronic phase is best reflected by the δ band power (Cohen, Navarro, Clemenceau, Baulac, & Miles, 2002; Putra et al., 2020), which was therefore determined in the third and fourth weeks. The calculated values were normalized to baseline activity, which was defined as the frequency power during several artifact- and epileptiform activity-free epochs (at least 10 min) within the last week of EEG recording. For spike analysis, EEG recordings were first high pass filtered at 1 Hz and then the number of EEG spikes exceeding 10-fold the SD of baseline activity was assessed using an automated spike detection protocol (NeuroScore). SD of baseline activity was calculated for every second of EEG recording during the above-mentioned epileptiform activity-free epochs.

2.3 | BrdU administration

Mice were given BrdU (1 mg/ml) through drinking water containing 1% sucrose for 14 days after kainate injection. BrdU administration was started 24 hr after kainate injection. From Day 16 after kainate injection, mice were given normal drinking water. On Day 30, anaesthetized mice were perfused with PBS followed by 4% PFA. Brains from these mice were subsequently fixed in 4% PFA for 12–16 hr. The next day, brains were transferred in vials containing PBS and stored until further use. Brains were cut into 40 μm thick coronal sections with a vibratome. The sections were stored in PBS containing 0.01% sodium azide.

2.4 | Immunofluorescence staining

Sections were incubated with 2 N HCl for 30 min. After washing with PBS, remaining HCl in the sections was neutralized by incubating the sections in 0.1 M borate buffer for 10 min. After permeabilization and blocking (2 hr, room temperature) with 0.5% Triton X-100 and 10% normal goat serum (NGS) (or 10% normal donkey serum [NDS]) in PBS, the sections were incubated overnight (4°C) in 5% NGS (or NDS) in PBS containing 0.1% Triton X-100 and the following primary antibodies: rat anti-BrdU (AbD

Serotec, 1:500); goat anti-CD31 (R & D systems, 1:200); goat anti-GFAP (Abcam, 1:500); mouse anti-NeuN (Merck, 1:500); goat anti-doublecortin (DCX) (Santacruz Biotech, 1:100); rabbit anti-Iba1 (Dako, 1:1,000); rabbit anti-Prox1 (Chemicon, 1:2,500). After washing three times with PBS (5 min each), the sections were incubated with secondary antibodies conjugated with Alexa Fluor 488, Alexa Fluor 594 or Alexa Fluor 647 (Invitrogen, dilution 1:500 each) in PBS with 2% NGS (or 2% NDS) and 0.1% Triton X-100 for 1.5 hr at room temperature.

2.5 | Imaging and cell counting

A confocal laser-scanning microscope (Leica TCS SP8, Wetzlar, Germany) was used for image acquisition. For cell counting, images were taken at $\times 40$ magnification (stacks of eight image planes with optical thickness of 1 μm each) while for assessing granule cell dispersion (GCD), $\times 10$ magnification (stacks of three image planes with optical thickness of 8 μm) was used. Image resolution was 1,024 \times 1,024 pixels. Cell counting in the dentate gyrus (DG) and CA1 regions was performed in 290 \times 290 \times 4 μm^3 counting boxes. The first counting box in the DG was positioned 250 μm away from the tip of the granule cell layer (GCL) while the other two boxes were positioned over the two blades of the GCL, adjacent to the first box. In the CA1 region, the three boxes were placed one after another in a row. Cell numbers were averaged across boxes within the same region.

2.6 | Quantification of GCD, astrogliosis, microglial activation, and vascular density

For GCD quantification, a continuous line was drawn from the tip of the hilus till the bend of the upper blade (Figure 3a). Another, vertical line (dotted, d) was drawn at the end of the continuous line, connecting the upper and lower blades of the DG. GCL width was measured at four positions named T1–T4. T1 and T2 were measured along Line D, T3, and T4 at a distance halfway between Line D and the tip of the hilus. The average of the four values was used as an indicator of the extent of GCD. For assessing microglial activation, numbers of BrdU positive microglia and areas occupied by Iba1 staining were determined. The extent of astrogliosis was estimated by calculating the area occupied by GFAP immunoreactivity. A point counting method was used to quantify the vascular density (Rigau et al., 2007). The resulting parameter called “point count” is influenced not only by the number of vessels present in a given area but also by the size and tortuosity of the vessels. Briefly, a 5 \times 5 squares grid (edge length of one square 116.25 μm) was superposed onto the digitized image. The numbers of intersections made by blood vessels with this grid were counted. At least three sections were used per mouse. The point counts were first averaged across sections and then across mice.

FIGURE 1 Kainate-induced seizure activity during *status epilepticus* (SE) and the chronic phase of epileptogenesis in DKO and wild-type (WT) mice. Kainate was stereotaxically injected into the deep layers of the neocortex above the right dorsal hippocampus. Electrographic seizures were continuously detected via cortical electrodes and telemetric transmitters. (a) Representative EEG traces recorded during SE in DKO and WT mice. (b) Quantification of number and duration of seizures, and total time spent in EEG seizures during the first hour after kainate injection. Seizures in DKO mice were of longer duration but less frequent. Total time spent in ictal activity was not different between DKO and WT mice. (c) The severity of SE was quantified by counting the number of EEG spikes exceeding at least tenfold baseline activity during the first 6 hr after kainate. No significant differences were observed between both genotypes. (d) Quantitative analysis of γ band EEG activity during SE in DKO and WT mice. γ band power was not influenced by the astrocytic uncoupling (inset, right). (e) Representative EEG traces recorded during spontaneous generalized seizures in DKO and WT mice. (f) Number and duration of spontaneous generalized seizures during the chronic phase (third and fourth weeks after kainate). Seizure frequency was significantly higher in DKO than in WT mice, while seizure duration was not different. (g) Averaged cumulative seizure burden in DKO and WT mice during the first 4 weeks after kainate injection. All values after Day 14 were significantly different between DKO and WT mice. (h) Spike frequency analysis detected significantly more spontaneous EEG spikes (exceeding at least tenfold baseline activity) during the third and fourth week post-SE, in DKO versus WT mice. Likewise, spectral analysis of spontaneous EEG activity during the same time period revealed higher δ band power in DKO mice. * $p < .05$ (t test). Boxes in box plots indicate interquartile range (IQR) with median (line) and mean (filled square); whiskers indicate 1.5 \times the IQR. $n = 9$ (DKO) and 8 (WT) animals [Color figure can be viewed at wileyonlinelibrary.com]

2.7 | Statistics

Data are given as mean \pm SD. Differences between groups were tested for significance using Student's t test or analysis of variance followed by Tukey's post hoc analysis. The level of significance was set at $p < .05$. Box plot data (Figure 1) are presented as Tukey boxes showing median (line), mean (filled square), and quartiles (25 and 75%; box). The whiskers extend to the highest and lowest values within 1.5 times interquartile range.

3 | RESULTS

3.1 | DKO mice exposed to the intracortical kainate model of MTLE-HS display unchanged overall SE severity but enhanced chronic seizure activity

To shed light on the role of astrocyte coupling in the development and progression of epilepsy, mice devoid of astrocytic GJ proteins

(DKO mice) were subjected to the unilateral intracortical kainate model of MTLE-HS. We have previously shown that this model reliably reproduces key morphological and functional features of chronic human MTLE with HS (Bedner et al., 2015). Continuous telemetric EEG recordings (24 hr/day for 4 weeks) and video monitoring were used to determine seizure activity during SE and the chronic phase. Kainate-induced SE was characterized by a series of generalized seizures lasting several hours (Figure 1a). For EEG quantification during SE, we examined the number and duration of seizures as well as the time spent in ictal activity during the first hour of recording. During this time window, an accurate determination of the duration of individual seizures was possible. The analysis revealed that in kainate-injected DKO mice, seizures during SE lasted significantly longer than in wild-type (WT) mice (91.8 ± 37.6 s vs. 47.4 ± 18.1 s, $p = .007$), but were less frequent (26.7 ± 15.5 seizures/hr vs. 53.7 ± 25.4 seizures/hr, $p = .01$). The total time spent in seizures was not different between genotypes (DKO: $57 \pm 17.7\%$; WT: $61.2 \pm 10.8\%$ of time, $p = .8$, Figure 1b).

Previous work has shown that SE in this MTLE model lasts about 4–5 hr (Bedner et al., 2015). To quantify total duration of SE, we counted during the first 6 hr of recording the number of EEG spikes with amplitudes exceeding baseline activity at least 7.5-fold. This analysis yielded no significant difference between kainate-injected DKO and WT mice (135.4 ± 86.6 spikes/min vs. 91.6 ± 69.8 spikes/min, $p = .3$, Figure 1c). Next, the same EEG data were subjected to spectral analysis using FFT and the power in the γ frequency range was compared. In accordance with spike frequency analysis, γ band power was not different between DKO and WT mice (10.8 ± 6.2 in DKO and 6.7 ± 5.2 in WT mice, $p = .2$, Figure 1d). Together, these findings indicate that astrocyte uncoupling affects the pattern of seizure activity during the initial phase of SE, but has no influence on overall SE severity.

All mice developed spontaneous generalized seizures after a latent period, the duration of which was not different between kainate-injected DKO and WT mice (3.75 ± 2.5 days vs. 3.62 ± 2 days, $p = .91$). Importantly, the frequency of spontaneous chronic seizures measured during the third and fourth week after epilepsy induction was more than twice as high in DKO mice than in WT mice (1.9 ± 1.1 vs. 0.8 ± 0.3 seizures/day, $p = .02$, Figure 1e). Likewise, the cumulative number of chronic seizures over total recording time (44.1 ± 25.2 vs. 22.37 ± 9.8 seizures, $p = .03$, Figure 1g) was significantly higher in kainate-injected DKO mice. There was, however, no difference in the duration of spontaneous seizures between both genotypes (DKO: 47.4 ± 6.9 s vs. WT: 44.2 ± 7.4 s, $p = .4$, Figure 1g). Spike frequencies were assessed during the third and fourth weeks of recording. Considering amplitudes exceeding baseline activity at least tenfold revealed a significantly higher frequency of spontaneous EEG spikes in DKO mice (317.1 ± 185.6 spikes/hr vs. 127.6 ± 48.4 spikes/hr, $p = .01$). Likewise, spectral EEG analysis demonstrated higher δ band power (2.7 ± 0.9 vs. 1.8 ± 0.4 , $p = .02$, Figure 1h) in DKO than in WT mice, indicating increased interictal activity in the former. The power in the other frequency bands was not elevated in DKO mice. Irrespective of genotype, all seizures observed by video monitoring were severe convulsions with rearing and falling (Stage V seizures according to

Racine's classification, Racine, 1972), indicating that the severity of spontaneous chronic seizures was not influenced by the lack of GJ proteins. Together the data suggest that deletion of astrocytic Cxs exacerbates chronic seizure burden without affecting SE severity.

3.2 | Kainate-injected DKO mice show unaltered neurodegeneration but less pronounced astrogliosis and GCD

About two thirds of patients with pharmacoresistant MTLE display HS, characterized by prominent neuronal loss in the CA1 and CA4 regions, reactive astrogliosis and GCD (Blümcke, Beck, Lie, & Wiestler, 1999). These histopathological changes are well reproduced in our animal model (Bedner et al., 2015). To explore whether the lack of astrocytic Cxs influences the development of HS, we performed immunohistochemical analyses of hippocampal slices from DKO and WT animals, 1 month after kainate injection. First, we assessed the extent of neurodegeneration and astrogliosis by NeuN/GFAP/Hoechst triple staining (Figure 2a). For quantification, the number of NeuN-positive cells was counted in an area of $260 \times 260 \times 15 \mu\text{m}^3$ within the CA1 *stratum pyramidale* underneath the injection side (ipsilateral side) and at the same position on the contralateral side. Ipsilaterally, NeuN-positive cells were reduced by almost 90% in both kainate-injected DKO and WT mice (DKO: by $83.2 \pm 22.4\%$; WT: by $86 \pm 16.4\%$ $p = .86$, Figure 2b). No neurodegeneration could be detected in the CA3 *stratum pyramidale*, neither in DKO nor in WT mice (WT: 413 ± 45.1 vs. 358.3 ± 58.2 NeuN⁺ cells, $p = .14$; DKO: 358.3 ± 42.7 vs. 393 ± 49.1 NeuN⁺ cells, $p = .1$, $n = 3$ slices from three animals for each group; analyzed area $581.3 \times 581.3 \times 8 \mu\text{m}^3$, data not shown). In contrast, the area occupied by GFAP immunoreactivity, which reflects the extent of reactive astrogliosis, was significantly smaller in the ipsilateral CA1 *stratum radiatum* of DKO versus WT mice (DKO: $144.6 \pm 33\%$; WT: $196.7 \pm 31.6\%$, $p = .03$, Figure 2b).

Next we quantified seizure-induced GCD in DKO and WT mice, 1 month after SE, by determining the width of the GCL blades visualized by Prox1 staining (Figure 3a). Ipsilaterally, the width (average of T1–T4) was significantly increased, both in DKO and WT mice, when compared with the corresponding contralateral hippocampi. Notably, in DKO mice, the increase was less pronounced than in the WT ($157.90 \pm 29.63 \mu\text{m}$ vs. $219.47 \pm 7.66 \mu\text{m}$, $p = .03$) (Figure 3b). These data indicate that astrocytic Cxs influence seizure-induced GCD. However, earlier studies have demonstrated that the number of Prox1-positive cells in Cx-deficient mice (DKO and Cx43 KO mice) is reduced compared to WT mice, due to impaired adult neurogenesis in the subgranular zone (Kunze et al., 2009; Zhang et al., 2018). To investigate whether this phenomenon accounts for the differences in GCD upon kainate injection, we compared the width of the GCL blades in untreated (nonepileptic) DKO and WT mice. The results revealed thinner blades in DKO than in WT mice ($54.5 \pm 5.4 \mu\text{m}$ vs. $69.4 \pm 2.9 \mu\text{m}$, $p = .01$, Suppl. Figure S1). Thus, the lower GCD found ipsilaterally in kainate-injected DKO mice might simply be a consequence of the reduced number of Prox1-positive cells in this genotype.

FIGURE 2 Loss of CA1 pyramidal neurons and reactive astrogliosis in DKO and wild-type (WT) mice in chronic mesial temporal lobe epilepsy. (a) NeuN (red)/GFAP (green)/Hoechst (blue) triple labeling in slices obtained from WT and DKO mice, 1 month after kainate injection. SP, *stratum pyramidale*; SR, *stratum radiatum*. Scale bar, 50 μm . (b) Quantification of the number of pyramidal neurons and GFAP immunoreactivity in an area of $260 \times 260 \times 15 \mu\text{m}^3$ within the CA1 subfield. The extent of astrogliosis, but not neurodegeneration, was reduced in DKO mice compared to WT mice. $*p < .05$ (analysis of variance [ANOVA] followed by post hoc Tukey's test). $n = 9$ slices from three animals per group [Color figure can be viewed at wileyonlinelibrary.com]

Taken together, immunohistochemical analyses indicated that, despite enhanced chronic seizure burden, deletion of astrocytic Cxs protects against the development of HS.

3.3 | Lower microglia activation in DKO mice 1 month after kainate injection

Activation of microglia is a primary inflammatory response to seizures (Eyo, Murugan, & Wu, 2017), which involves hypertrophy and process elongation of microglia and stimulation of proliferation (Avignone,

Lepleux, Angibaud, & Nägerl, 2015; Avignone, Ulmann, Levavasseur, Rassendren, & Audinat, 2008). Using Iba1/BrdU double immunostaining, we assessed whether spontaneous chronic seizures differently affect microglia in DKO versus WT mice. One month after kainate injection, irrespective of genotype, the area occupied by microglia was increased ipsilaterally, both in the CA1 region and in the DG (Figure 4a,b,e, f). In the CA1 region, but not the DG, this increase was accompanied by a rise in the number of BrdU-positive Iba1 cells, indicating increased microglial proliferation (Figure 4a–d). Interestingly, microglial proliferation/activation in the ipsilateral CA1 region of DKO mice was lower than in WT mice, as indicated by the density of Iba1/BrdU-double-positive cells (76.8 ± 6.7 vs. 100 ± 11.1 per counting box, $p = .03$) and the area occupied by Iba1 immunoreactivity ($11,201.5 \pm 1,348 \mu\text{m}^2$ vs. $7,521.7 \pm 650.6 \mu\text{m}^2$, $p = .01$, Figure 4d,f). Together, these data indicate that astrocytic Cxs increase chronic seizure-induced microglial activation in the hippocampus.

3.4 | DKO mice have reduced seizure-induced angiogenesis

Angiogenesis is enhanced in epilepsy and it starts before the onset of spontaneous seizures (Newton, Girgenti, Collier, & Duman, 2006; Rigau et al., 2007). Endothelial cell proliferation is the hallmark of angiogenesis (Hellsten, Wennström, Bengzon, Mohapel, & Tingström, 2004). We used coimmunostaining of CD31 and BrdU to visualize newly generated endothelial cells. One month after kainate injection, the ipsilateral hippocampus displayed enhanced endothelial proliferation when compared with the corresponding contralateral side (Figure 5). In WT mice, the ipsilateral density of CD31/BrdU double-positive cells was more than threefold higher than contralaterally, both in the DG (14.66 ± 0.6 vs. 4.55 ± 2.7 cells per counting box, $p = .0008$, Figure 5). In DKO mice, the increase was less pronounced (DG, 8.3 ± 2.6 vs. 3.1 ± 0.8 cells per counting box, $p = .03$; CA1, 12.66 ± 2.6 vs. 5.33 ± 3.2 cells per counting box, $p = .04$, Figure 5). Importantly, the ipsilateral hippocampus of DKO mice showed a significantly lower density of CD31/BrdU double-positive cells compared to WT mice (Figure 5c,d). These data indicate that chronic seizure-induced endothelial cell proliferation is modulated by astrocytic Cxs. Next, we assessed vascular density using CD31 immunostaining. A point counting method was employed as reported previously (Rigau et al., 2007). In WT mice, a higher density of CD31-positive details was found on the ipsilateral versus contralateral side (ipsilateral: 81.55 ± 8.94 ; contralateral: 57.55 ± 6.40 , $p = .02$) while DKO mice were not affected (ipsilateral: 60.33 ± 1.76 ; contralateral: 50.55 ± 14.41 , $p = .3$, Figure 5e,f). This finding further supports an important role of astrocytic GJ proteins in chronic seizure-induced angiogenesis.

3.5 | Chronic seizure-induced neurogenesis is independent of astrocytic Cxs

While it is well established that seizures enhance adult hippocampal neurogenesis (e.g., Hüttmann et al., 2003), Kunze et al. (2009) showed that

FIGURE 3 Seizure-induced granule cell dispersion (GCD) is attenuated in DKO mice. (a) Prox1 immunostaining, 1 month after kainate injection. Ipsilaterally, granule cells are dispersed in contrast to the compact cellular architecture in the contralateral hippocampus. T1–T4 indicate the positions of width evaluation of the granule cell layer (GCL), which were averaged to determine GCD. T1 and T2 are taken along Lines D, T3, and T4 at a distance halfway between Line D and the tip of the hilus. Scale bar, 100 μm . (b) Quantification of GCD 1 month after kainate using the average width of the GCL (μm). The ipsilateral width of the GCL significantly exceeded the contralateral side. GCD was less pronounced in DKO mice. * $p < .05$ [analysis of variance [ANOVA] followed by post hoc Tukey's test]. $n = 9$ slices from three animals per group [Color figure can be viewed at wileyonlinelibrary.com]

under control (nonseizure) conditions, Cxs are essential for adult neurogenesis. However, it is not known whether seizure-induced neurogenesis is also influenced by Cxs. This question was addressed in DKO and WT mice, using triple labeling for Prox1, BrdU, and DCX (Figure 6a,b). Prox1 was used as a marker for mature granule cells, DCX to detect immature/newly born neurons and BrdU to label proliferating and newly generated cells. In agreement with previous findings, under control conditions (i.e., no kainate injection) neurogenesis was significantly impaired in DKO mice (DCX + BrdU, DKO: 1.3 ± 0.3 vs. WT: 2.6 ± 0.3 cells per counting box, $p = .008$; Prox1 + BrdU, DKO: 1.9 ± 0.4 vs. WT: 3.8 ± 0.4 cells per counting box, $p = .003$; Suppl. Figure S2). Next, kainate injections were performed and 1 month later, the sclerotic hippocampi located underneath the injection side were analyzed in DKO and WT mice. No DCX-positive or Prox1/BrdU-double-positive cells could be detected in that area, neither in DKO nor in WT mice (Figure 6a), showing that neurogenesis is completely absent in the dorsal ipsilateral DG. This finding is in agreement with earlier observations from the intrahippocampal kainate injection model of MTLE with HS (Häussler, Bielefeld, Froriep, Wolfart, & Haas, 2012). Similar to the latter study, we found strongly increased neurogenesis in the contralateral hippocampus. Although the number of DCX/BrdU- and Prox1/BrdU-positive cells was contralaterally higher in WT versus DKO mice (Figure 6c), the relative increase in seizure-induced neurogenesis was similar in both lines (DCX + BrdU, DKO: $612.7 \pm 243.6\%$ vs. WT: $582.9 \pm 124.8\%$, $p = .9$; Prox1 + BrdU, DKO: $634.6 \pm 335.7\%$ vs. WT: $684.9 \pm 139.9\%$, $p = .8$, Figure 6d). This implies that astrocytic Cxs are not involved in the seizure-induced increase of adult neurogenesis.

4 | DISCUSSION

We have previously shown that hippocampal astrocytes in human and experimental MTLE-HS lose coupling via GJ channels and that this uncoupling starts already before the onset of neurodegeneration and chronic seizure activity, hinting at a causative role in the initiation of MTLE (Bedner et al., 2015). The assumption that the astroglial network possesses antiepileptic properties is mainly based on the spatial K^+ buffering concept, according to which excessive extracellular K^+ released during neuronal activity is taken up by astrocytes, redistributed through the astrocytic network and released at regions of lower extracellular K^+ concentrations (Orkand, Nicholls, & Kuffler, 1966). According to this concept, loss of GJ-mediated coupling would result in accumulation of extracellular K^+ , neuronal depolarization and a lowered threshold for seizure generation. It would also depolarize astrocytes and reduce their glutamate uptake capacity, which again would promote seizure activity due to prolonged activation of excitatory synapses. Indeed, enhanced extracellular glutamate concentrations have been found in the cerebral fluid of MTLE patients (Cavus et al., 2005). However, the astroglial network has also been proposed to have proepileptic effects (Chever et al., 2016; Rouach et al., 2008). To elucidate consequences of astrocyte uncoupling on the development of chronic MTLE, we used transgenic mice lacking Cx30 and Cx43 in astrocytes. These mice are hyperexcitable in situ (Wallraff et al., 2006) but no spontaneous seizures or abnormal EEG activity was detected in vivo (Chever et al., 2016). We subjected DKO mice to our MTLE model and continuously assessed seizure activity over a period of 1 month. Despite a similar strength of kainate-induced SE in WT and DKO mice, on a long term, we observed a

FIGURE 4 Reduced microglial activation in DKO mice in chronic mesial temporal lobe epilepsy. (a,b) Iba1 (white) and BrdU (red) double immunostaining in the DG and CA1 region of wild-type (WT) and DKO mice, 1 month after kainate injection. Colocalization of BrdU with Iba1 indicates newly generated or proliferating microglia (examples indicated by arrows). Dashed-line demarcates the subgranular zone (SGZ) from the GCL. ML, molecular layer; SR, *stratum radiatum*. Scale bar, 50 μm. (c–d) Quantification of microglial activation 1 month after kainate by counting newly generated microglia and estimating the area occupied by Iba1 immunoreactivity in counting boxes (290 × 290 × 8 μm³). (c,d) In both genotypes, ipsilaterally the density of BrdU-positive microglia was increased in the CA1 region, but not in the DG. This increase was significantly less in DKO versus WT mice. (e,f) The area occupied by Iba1 immunoreactivity was increased in the ipsilateral DG and CA1 region of both, DKO and WT mice. This increase was significantly less pronounced in the CA1 region of DKO mice. **p* < .05 [analysis of variance [ANOVA] followed by post hoc Tukey's test]. *n* = 9 slices from three animals per group [Color figure can be viewed at wileyonlinelibrary.com]

higher frequency of spontaneous generalized chronic seizures in mice lacking astrocytic Cxs, indicating an antiepileptic function of astrocyte coupling. One has of course to consider that astrocyte uncoupling in DKO mice differs from the acquired loss of coupling upon kainate injection or in human MTLE-HS. First, as Cx43 deletion in DKO mice occurs early in development (at around embryonic Day 13; Theis et al., 2003) and Cx30 is constitutively lacking, compensatory developmental changes are likely to occur. Indeed, astrocytic glutamate uptake, excitatory synaptic transmission and plasticity as well as adult neurogenesis in the DG are altered in these mice (Kunze et al., 2009; Pannasch et al., 2011; Pannasch et al., 2014). Second, DKO mice not only lack intercellular coupling but also the GJ proteins while in the

sclerotic hippocampus of human and experimental MTLE even increased Cx43 levels have been observed (Deshpande et al., 2017). Indeed, in our previous study, we found strong evidence that subcellular reorganization and augmented Cx43 phosphorylation (at Serine 255 and 368) account for the loss of coupling in human and experimental epilepsy (Deshpande et al., 2017). It is known that phosphorylation of Cx43 at these residues reduces intercellular coupling without compromising (GJ) or Cx hemichannel formation (Lampe et al., 2000; Thévenin et al., 2013; Warn-Cramer, Cottrell, Burt, & Lau, 1998). Thus, channel-independent effects of Cx proteins may influence synaptic transmission and seizure activity in WT but not in DKO mice (Pannasch et al., 2014; Pannasch, Dossi, Ezan, & Rouach, 2019).

FIGURE 5 Reduced endothelial proliferation and vascular density in DKO mice in chronic mesial temporal lobe epilepsy. (a,b) CD31 (green) and BrdU (red) double immunostaining in the DG and CA1 region of wild-type (WT) and DKO mice 1 month after kainate injection. Colocalization of BrdU with CD31 indicates newly generated or proliferating endothelial cells (examples indicated by arrows). Dotted line demarcates the subgranular zone (SGZ) of the DG. ML, molecular layer; SR, *stratum radiatum*. Scale bar, 50 μm . (c,d) Number of BrdU-positive CD31 cells per counting box ($290 \times 290 \times 8 \mu\text{m}^3$) in the DG (c) and CA1 region (d) 1 month after kainate. In both regions, the ipsilateral side showed more endothelial cell proliferation than the corresponding contralateral side. However, DKO mice showed less proliferation than WT mice, indicating a modulatory role of astrocytic Cxs on angiogenesis. (e) CD31 immunostaining in hippocampal slices, 1 month after kainate injection. CD31 delineates blood vessels. Scale bar, 100 μm . (f) For quantification of vascular density 1 month after kainate, the “point counting method” was applied to confocal images from the CA1 region. The bar graphs show point counts normalized to the contralateral side. In WT mice, ipsilaterally the vascular density was 141.7% of the contralateral hippocampus. In DKO mice, this difference disappeared. * $p < .05$ (analysis of variance [ANOVA] followed by post hoc Tukey’s test). $n = 9$ slices from three animals per group and staining condition [Color figure can be viewed at wileyonlinelibrary.com]

Finally, one has to consider that astrocyte uncoupling in human and experimental MTLE is spatially restricted to the sclerotic area and the epileptic foci, while Cx deletion in DKO mice concerns the entire brain. Thus, lack of GJ proteins and hemichannels in DKO mice might partially counteract the proepileptic effect of uncoupling, which offers an explanation for the lack of seizures in untreated mice and the relatively moderate hyperexcitability found in acute brain slices obtained from these mice (Wallraff et al., 2006).

Applying our MTLE-HS model (Bedner et al., 2015), quantification of epileptic activity (time spent in ictal activity) during SE, that is, the first hours after kainate injection, revealed no significant difference between DKO and WT mice. Thus, it is unlikely that the higher number of subsequently developing spontaneous chronic seizures in DKO mice was simply a consequence of a more severe SE. In a recent study, i.p. injection of PTZ was used to investigate the role of astrocyte coupling in acute hyperexcitability (up to 30 min after injection).

(a) *Ipsilateral DG*

(c)

(d)

FIGURE 6 Neurogenesis does not require astrocytic Cxs in chronic mesial temporal lobe epilepsy. (a,b) Prox1 (white), BrdU (red), and DCX (green) triple immunostaining in slices from wild-type (WT) and DKO mice, 1 month after kainate injection. BrdU was administered through drinking water till Day 14. (a) No DCX-positive cells were detected in the ipsilateral DG, irrespective of the genotype. Furthermore, no colocalization of Prox1 and BrdU was observed, confirming lack of newly born granule cells. Scale bar, 50 μ m. (b) Contralaterally, abundant DCX/BrdU and Prox1/BrdU colocalization was seen in both, DKO and WT mice. Arrows indicate newly born neurons, colabeled with all three markers. Scale bar, 50 μ m. (c,d) Quantification of Prox1/BrdU- and DCX/BrdU-double-positive cells 1 month after kainate, using counting boxes ($290 \times 290 \times 4 \mu\text{m}^3$) positioned 250 μ m away from the outermost margin of the GCL flexure, oriented perpendicularly to the longitudinal axis of the GCL. Although the density of Prox1/BrdU- and DCX/BrdU-positive cells was significantly lower in DKO mice, the relative increase of these values in the epileptic versus nonepileptic condition was similar in both genotypes. * $p < .05$ (t test). n.s., not significant. $n = 9$ slices from three animals per group [Color figure can be viewed at wileyonlinelibrary.com]

In this model, more but shorter seizures were observed in DKO mice (Chever et al., 2016). The present study did not intend to analyze the mechanisms of SE generation, but addressed the consequences of astrocyte Cx deficiency on epileptogenesis post-SE, that is, development and progression of spontaneous chronic seizures. By exerting a similar acute seizure burden in DKO and WT mice, we consider our

model well suited to investigate the role of the astroglial coupling network on the pathogenesis of MTLE.

Despite the higher frequency of spontaneous chronic seizures, the extent of neurodegeneration was not significantly different between Cx-deficient and WT mice. Given the important role of the astroglial network in glutamate and K^+ buffering as well as in the

efficient supply of energetic metabolites one would expect exacerbated neurodegeneration in DKO mice. In line with this assumption, Cx43 KO mice exhibited larger infarct volumes after induced ischemia (Nakase, Fushiki, & Naus, 2003; Siushansian, Bechberger, Cechetto, Hachinski, & Naus, 2001). On the other hand, several studies indicated that astrocyte GJ channels mediate propagation and amplification of cell injury by allowing intercellular diffusion of toxic/stress molecules (Frantseva, Kokarotseva, & Perez Velazquez, 2002; Lin et al., 1998). Possibly, these two opposite effects of astrocyte uncoupling compensate each other in our experimental approach. The immunohistochemical analyses further revealed attenuated astrogliosis, microglial activation, and angiogenesis in Cx-deficient mice. These phenomena might be attributed to the lack of Cx hemichannels, which were thought to be involved in the regulation of microglial chemotaxis and process elongation via release of ATP (Davalos et al., 2005). Furthermore, elevated ATP levels amplify inflammation through NALP3 inflammasome activation not only in microglia but also in other brain cell types (Bours, Dagnelie, Giuliani, Wesselius, & Di Virgilio, 2011; Zhou, Green, Bennet, Gunn, & Davidson, 2019). The limited inflammatory responses in DKO mice in turn could be responsible for the attenuated astrogliosis and angiogenesis, as the mutual influence of these processes is well-documented (Jackson, Seed, Kircher, Willoughby, & Winkler, 1997; Sofroniew & Vinters, 2010).

Another point to consider is that the cortical electrodes used in this study are not appropriate for detection of focal seizure activity within the hippocampus. The frequency of such seizures may differ from those recorded in the cortex and may correlate with the extent of histopathological alterations. Further studies, for instance using hippocampal depth electrodes, are required to elucidate this question.

Previous work of our group demonstrated that GJ channel-dependent functions of Cx43 (but not of Cx30) are involved in the regulation of adult neurogenesis in the DG. Indeed, in DKO as well as in Cx43 KO mice proliferation and the number of radial glia-like cells were substantially reduced (Kunze et al., 2009; Zhang et al., 2018), indicating that intercellular transfer of molecules through Cx43 GJ channels is necessary for proper neurogenesis. In the present study, we found that chronic seizures similarly potentiate adult neurogenesis in WT and DKO mice, suggesting that physiological and chronic seizure-induced neurogenesis are differentially regulated.

Collectively, the present data provide new insights as to how astrocyte GJ proteins and channels may contribute to the development of chronic epilepsy. The finding that DKO mice display a higher frequency of spontaneous generalized chronic seizures supports the view that loss of astrocyte coupling as observed in human and experimental MTLE-HS represents a crucial event in the pathogenesis of the disease. Molecules specifically acting as GJ activators and restoring astrocyte coupling in the epileptic brain might therefore allow for the development of new therapeutic approaches.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare no potential conflict of interest.

DATA AVAILABILITY STATEMENT

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

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